

THE FORMATION OF THE URBAN IN THE CITY OF JIZZAH IN THE MIDDLE AGES

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Anatation: The article describes the creative work, culture, way of life, architecture of human settlements in the first and second half of the Middle Ages in Jizzakh.

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It is known that, according to the reports of the medieval authors, the city of Jizzakh adopted Islam in the 9th-10th centuries from the plundering campaigns of pastoralist nomadic peoples. It was famous as the main headquarters of the "Islamic Army Ghazis" who defended Ustrushona and Sogd lands. The basis of "Ghazis" was formed by descendants, "Khojas" who descended from Fatima, the daughter of Muhammad Alaihis Salam, and her son-in-law Caliph Ali. The purpose of presenting these thoughts is that the "Khoja Roziyan" cemetery began its activity at least in the 9th-10th centuries and is directly related to the "activities of the ghazis" in Jizzakh. If the historical truth of these ideas is fully proven, the location of the city of Jizzakh in the 9th-10th centuries will be clarified. It is worth noting that a group of experts recognized the place of the city of Jizzakh in the developed Middle Ages as the Urn of Qaliyatepa.

However, M.Pardaev claims that instead of Jizzakh in the middle ages, along with Kaliyatepa, Orda is also a "contender". The reason why the author comes to this opinion is the fact that the construction remains of the 9th-13th centuries are found in a very small area in the cultural layers of Qaliyatepa. According to the information given to us by M. Pardaev, the fact that "Khoja Roziyan" cemetery is located near Orda and not near Kaliyatepa is also important in this matter. From this, it can be said that the residence of the "Ghazis" was not in Kaliyatepa, but in Orda. By the way, a number of old tombstones have been preserved in "Khoja Roziyan". If these tombstones are read and studied in the future and the identity of the corpses is determined, their periodic levels are determined, it is inevitable that important innovations will be introduced to the above-mentioned issues of the history of the city of Jizzakh.

To ensure the security of the city of Jizzakh, the outskirts of the city were surrounded by a wall, and there were Samarkand, Tashkent, Oratepa and Bukhara gates for entry and exit. The gates were guarded and protected by

soldiers day and night. The first of these gates leads to Samarkand, the second to Tashkent, and the third to Bukhara. Residents of "Kunchilik", "Jizzakhlik", "Zargarlik", "Aqqorganlik" neighborhoods of the city were engaged in trade, crafts, pottery, soap making.

Each city was protected from the enemies of the Horde, which was a fortress consisting of an ark and a city, and surrounding neighborhoods. To protect against the external enemy, a moat was dug outside the wall of the Horde fortress and filled with water. The Horde fortress was destroyed in 1866 and was not restored.

And this does not reveal to us many secrets that we can know about Orda, many historical monuments have been destroyed over time or people have completely forgotten those places.

In the past, we can see many examples that people do not just leave the places where they live, but on the contrary, there are many reasons such as invasions, inability to raise livestock, droughts, etc. for example; As a result of planned excavations carried out on the site of the Orda fortress (now in the yard of the Jizzakh spinning factory), the remains of an underground passage (secret lahm) dating back to the 18th-19th centuries were found. According to the archaeologist M. Pardayev, this secret passage starts from the arch of Orda Castle and goes all the way to the northeast.) was made, its width is 1.8 meters, height is 2.2 meters, and it turned out that the upper part is closed in the form of an arch.

At a distance of 6-8 meters from both side walls of the underground corridor, special shelves were made of bricks of the size mentioned above, and torches were placed on them for lighting. This underground corridor served for the protection of the governor of the Horde fortress and his relatives during the military operations. The size of the secret underground corridor indicates that not only people, but also horsemen had the opportunity to leave the fortress with their horses.

In the Middle Ages, Jizzakh became a victim of many invasions, so we can learn that secret exits were always built in fortresses.

The land of Jizzakh flourished during the Timurid era. But in the 16th and 19th centuries, people had to go through many battles and robberies.

The Mongol invasion led to the collapse of the main fortresses and fortifications. During Shaibani Khan's time, they were almost completely destroyed. The inhabitants of Jizzakh land were feudal lords, conflicts between governors, raids organized by the khans of the Kipchak desert, the wars that occurred during the

reign of Abdullah Khan and the Khan of the Kipchak desert Babakh Ota and the governor of Tashkent, Darvishkhan, cost a lot of money, so the city of Jizzakh Many monuments and cities were destroyed and treasures and antiques were looted and did not reach us.

During its glorious history, Jizzakh was a part of the Somanids, Karakhanids, Khorezmshahs, Timurids, Bukhara Khanate and Emirate, as well as Tsarist Russia. Old Jizzakh has always been the center of attention of foreign invaders with its serunum lands, unique nature, diverse wealth and strategically important geographical location.

But the gates of the city were never easily opened to the invaders, and a valiant fight was always waged against the enemy. That's why Jizzakh was in crisis several times and was destroyed. However, this ancient city-fort has been restored again and again.

For this reason, studying the Horde and its surrounding areas, identifying the boundaries of the distribution of fragments of pottery belonging to the material culture of the Horde, collecting ethnographic data, opinions expressed by informants - interlocutors and comparing them to topographic plans, comparative o Through the study, important clarifications were made to the general area, borders, and historical topography of the Jizzakh Land (Horde) during the Khanate period. It was found out from the research that the plan of Orda was made on a scale of 1x5000 cm (that is, 50 m in 1 cm). According to the topographic plan, Orda has a rectangular shape.

The size of its sides extending in the north-south direction is 1100x900 m. A square-shaped arch is located in the middle of the square. Its sides are equal to 300x200 m. Based on these figures, the total area of the Horde is almost 100 hectares, and its width is 6 hectares. can be said to have organized

The fact that the Horde flourished in its time can be seen from the finds, literature, and the works of historians.

According to the elders of Jizzakh, the defense walls of the Horde were so long, high and wide that the guards rode around on the wall in horse-drawn carts and guarded the city. The cart of guards coming from the opposite side continued its way without destroying each other. According to the topographic plan, the total length of the defense walls of Orda reached 4 km.

In the system of defensive walls, there were defensive towers at a certain distance. These semi-circular constellations are mostly densely located on the northern and eastern walls of the Horde. This shows from which direction the forces that threatened the Horde came and moved.

On the outer side of the defensive walls, the location of water-filled ditches was noted. A suspension bridge was erected in front of all three gates to enter the city. According to Akhmad Donish, who wrote the history of the Managite dynasty, so that the gates of the Jizzakh Horde could not be breached by the Russians, dirt was brought inside the gates on carts. According to the author's writing, when the Russian soldiers stormed the Horde through the Oratepa gate after a long-lasting attack and efforts, all the defenders' exit routes were closed, and they had the opportunity to open the gates of Tashkent and Samarkand. did not Because of this, many Jizzakh defenders died by throwing themselves over the 10 m high walls.

According to the topographical map, the northern and eastern gates of Orda, that is, Tashkent and Oratepa gates, were completely destroyed during the storming, only the western Samarkand gate survived.

The population lived densely in the village. We can know this from the information of our informants and the topographical map. Neighborhoods started almost behind the defensive walls, there are almost no open spaces in these areas, the streets are extremely narrow, connected to each other, and all these streets lead to the square of the Horde governor's arch. There was an open area around the arch.

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